

The Gideons International in Nigeria

Data source: Database of religion history (DRH)

By Abimbola Adesoji, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ilife, Nigeria

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Christianity, Religious Group, Language, Evangelicalism, Protestantism, Born Again Christianity, English, Yoruba Language

The entry relates to the establishment/inauguration of the Gideons International in Nigeria since 1964 and its growth and activities since then including the ways it has impacted the country and the extent of the success of its activities. The Gideons International in Nigeria is an association of Christian Business and Professional men who have accepted the Lordship of Jesus and committed to making Christ known through their witnessing, association for Christ and the distribution of the Bibles in the traffic lanes of lives. Traffic lanes of life are places that the association believes that people will pass through at least once in their lifetime. These are schools, hospitals, hotels, motels, police and army formations as well as prisons. The ultimate aim of the association is that every soul encountered in the traffic lanes of life will come to the saving knowledge of the Lord and Saviour, Jesus Christ. The association is a part of a worldwide association that operates in 199 countries of the world and distributes bibles printed in 109 different languages. The language of the Bible distributed in Nigeria is English. It came into being in the United States of America in 1899 through the inspiration of God to John H Nicolson and Samuel E Hill. The name Gideons derives from the story of the Biblical Gideon in the sixth and seventh chapters of the Book of Judges. The Biblical Gideon was a man who was willing to do exactly what God wanted him to do, irrespective of his own judgement as to the plans or results. Humility, faith and obedience were his great elements of character, a standard that the Association is trying to establish in all its members. An integral part of the Association is the auxiliary, which comprises the wives of Gideons who meet the same spiritual qualifications. Ultimately, the association is a family ministry where every member of the family has a part. The Auxiliary are expected to be on their knees praying for the Gideons to be on their feet placing Bibles and witnessing. To be spiritually qualified to be a Gideon and a part of the association, a person must believe in the Bible as the inspired Word of God, believe in the Lord Jesus Christ as the eternal Son of God, have received Jesus as his personal Saviour and endeavour to follow Him in his daily lives. In addition, a person must believe in the endless lake of fire for the unsaved, accept the Biblical standard of marriage being between one biological man and one biological woman. In addition he must be a member in good standing of an Evangelical or Protestant church, congregation or assembly and should willingly participate in the activities of a camp, a smaller units into which the association is divided. One must also be professionally qualified by being engaged in a work for which one gets regular income. This could be by working for government, other people or being self employed in a business, trade or vocations. The Association is guided by and lay emphasis on the importance of fulfilling seven Spiritual Objectives: being men and women of the Book (the Bible, the Gideon Guide Book, Cheque Book (for giving), Diary for keeping records) Prayer, Faith, Separated Walk, Compassionate Heart, who Witness and Give. Funding for the mission of the Association is secured through personal contributions and bequests, church offerings, and through the GideonCard Bible Programme (a programme through which members and Believers generally give in honour of their ceremonies (Birthdays, wedding anniversaries, among other ceremonies) or in memory of dear ones, for the printing and placement of scriptures. Since 1964 when the first camp was established in Nigeria, there are 281 camps as at March 2024. These camps have been differently organised in the past as zones. They are now grouped into seven state structures namely South-West, Central-West, North-West, North-East, Central-East, South-East and Central-South each under the direction of a trustee who also doubles as the state president and who is responsible to a national cabinet elected annually at the national convention of the association. The national cabinet comprising the president, vice-president, treasurer secretary/executive director, chaplain

and the seven state trustees is complemented by the national auxiliary cabinet which comprises the auxiliary president, vice-president, secretary/treasurer and chaplain. The national cabinet operates under the authority and direction of the International Cabinet which is also elected annually at the International convention. The national cabinet positions are replicated at the camp level but with programme leaders (church relations, faith fund, scripture distribution, gideoncard, membership) appointed. Regional Directors in state associations and Area leaders like Area Directors and programme leaders at the state and area levels are appointed. Since 1964, the association has placed over 80 million scriptures in nooks and crannies of Nigeria as part of over 2.3 billion scriptures that the Gideons in different countries of the world have placed.

Date Range: 1964 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Africa, Europe, North America, South America, Central America, Europe, Middle East, Asia, Australia, New Zealand

Region tags: Europe, North America, Middle East, Africa, South America, Global, South Asia, Nigeria, New Zealand, Taiwan, United Kingdom

RCCG is rapidly spreading around the world. It is represented in about 197 countries and regions worldwide.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Information Bulletin of the Gideons International in Nigeria, October to december 2020
Published by The Gideons International in Nigeria, 56, Falolu Road, Surulere Lagos

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://gideons.org.ng>
– Source 1 Description: The Gideons International in Nigeria
– Source 2 URL: https://www.gideons.org/FC_Nigeria
– Source 2 Description: Nigeria
– Source 3 URL: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com>
– Source 3 Description: We distributed 74.6 million bibles in Nigeria in 55 years- Gideons International

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: YouTube.Channel7 TV
– Source 1 Description: 15th State Convention/The Gideons International in Nigeria-You Tube
– Source 2 URL: <https://docplayer.net/204275422>
– Source 2 Description: The Gideons International in Nigeria -PDF Free Download

– Source 3 URL: Facebook. The Gideons International in NigeriaFacebook

– Source 3 Description: Love In Action in NigeriaFacebook

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The nature of contact involves the Gideons reaching out to other religious groups through witnessing and distribution of the Bible and Testaments with a view to winning them for the Lord. This is done through regular witnessing and bible placements in schools and other traffic lanes of life and occasionally through Bible Blitzes (mass distribution of the testament in targeted locations)

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: It is not a case of struggling with others or imposing idea or faith on them but a case of presenting Christ through the scripture and quietly withdrawing in case of rejection or opposition.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Yes it is most of the time accommodating. It can also be hostile some of the time like some people inciting their religious groups not to accept Gideon testament or to throw it away or tear in a few extreme situations.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: It can be neutral some of the time

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: In some parts of Nigeria where Islamic religion is strong. But in most cases, such is prevented by carefully studying the situation and pre-empting conflict through withdrawal or non-distribution /or non-proselytising

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There could be some opposition or violence in region dominated by Islam but such violence are mostly pre-empted by avoidance or quick withdrawal some of the time.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: By formal application for membership having met the requirement or qualification for membership. These include being born again, being a member of a protestant or evangelical denomination or assembly and having a regular work or a business

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: The starting age of enrollment is being a young adult who has left college or university and is gainfully employed

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Whereas a male adult enrolls for membership, all members of his family become members of the association either at the point of enrolment if he is married or when he gets married later and have children

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Notes: There is no special or hidden ritual. But a prospect whose application has been approved by the membership committee of the Association at the national level is issued a membership card, a Guide Book and a Bible and is formally and openly decorated as a member at the camp level into which the association is divided.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The association engages in regular witnessing at the camp level, mostly weekly, and the state and national association levels during state and national convention which holds annually in

designated places. An area or a region that is considered not properly or regularly evangelised is earmarked for scripture blitzes during which period extensive witnessing also take place.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: It is mandatory in the sense that all members are usually persuaded of the importance attached scripture distribution and witnessing (evangelism). However, if for one reason or the other a member is not able to join in such assignments, there are usually no consequences for such unavoidable absence.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: The form of missionary work the group engages in include financial contribution for the purpose of printing more bible for distribution and going to areas where the Gideons are less prominent (bible blitz) for massive bible placement and distribution.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Missionary work is mandated for all adherents because of the joint responsibility each member feels towards attaining the group's goals.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: The group's proselytising approach is not coercive. It is persuasive.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Occasionally, the support of government leaders is sought to facilitate the clearing of scriptures which are brought from the United States if there is bureaucratic delays or the charges are enormous (for special waivers)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Whoever renounces his faith/belief in the atoning sacrifice of the Lord Jesus and his sacrificial death on the cross automatically ceases to be a member.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 4183

Notes: The number comprises 2309 Gideons and 1874 Auxiliary members (auxiliary members are the wives of the Gideons who have enrolled as members).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.000020915

Notes: In a population of over 200,000,000 according to estimates, the total number of adherents is very very small yet makes impact

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: The Gideons International in Nigeria, apart from being a part of the Association in the other 198 countries of the world, is seen, conceived, and operates as an arm of the church. So it relates with church members and pastors, draws membership mostly from the church and goes to the church to give Gideon message/report annually and is supported by the church with offerings and money gifts for the printing of scriptures

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Elected leadership exists at the national, state and camp levels while appointed leaders exist at area and programme levels. National and State leaders are elected annually at the association's convention and the camp level usually in the month of May of every year

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Hierarchy exist not in terms of any special qualification but mainly for the purpose of coordination. Oftentimes, the silent principle in leadership emergence is leaders moving up until they get to the highest position (in this case the national or state president)

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

Notes: Although each camp, which is the smallest and most important organ of the association usually has a tenured President who oversees the affairs of the camp, the President is usually supported by an executive committee which runs the affairs of the camp for a predetermined/specified period of time.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: Camps within close proximity to each other are grouped together to form an Area while Areas are grouped together to form a State. A group of States within a national boundary form a National Association. Leaders exist at each level of these structures and are responsible to those directly above them in the structure. It is important to stress that the form of servant leadership that exists in the group allows for executives to rise in the leadership structure while at the same time also serving under local leaders in their camps.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The group has an elected National Association President. However, the National Executive Director oversees the National Secretariat and is responsible for the day to day running of the National Association.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 4

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: Leaders are only expected to be born again, led by the spirit of God and have enough resources including money to attend meetings of the association. He must however have demonstrated leadership qualities by precedents(in earlier position or offices he has occupied)

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Mostly by elections. Only Area and Programme Leaders are appointed

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: Leaders emerge through elections

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

Notes: Members elect new leaders

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– Yes

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers are often offered to the supernatural being before elections are held for filling vacant positions in the group.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: They can make mistake but are accepted if they are willing to accept their errors and for as long as their errors are not injurious to the name or standing of the association

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Notes: Any member of the group may bring up a matter of fallibility of their leaders which has come to their notice to the group's attention. Such matters may be investigated and a position taken after due consideration of facts available to the group.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is also possible.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: Political rulers do not get involved in the affairs of the group

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: There is a Guide Book and other regulations that guide how a leader should act and what is expected of the followership. Whatever is not in accordance with this is not allowed or respected or followed

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Association believes only in the Bible as the inspired, infallible and inerrant word of God

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible . There is no other scripture

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Notes: There is no scripture apart from the Bible but we relate with the story of the establishment of the association which we share everywhere

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There is the National Office which coordinates the affairs of the association in Lagos. Currently the association is constructing a new National Office which will be dedicated for use in August 2024

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: The group has a long tradition of holding their meetings in halls and auditoriums in public places in their localities. They avoid using church buildings of local assemblies around them to avoid being identified with a denomination. This is because they are non-denominational and prefer to retain the diversity of their membership from different church denominations.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that those accepted the Lordship of Jesus and daily work with him will reign in eternal bliss in paradise with the Lord Jesus Christ. This paradise in heaven is different from Hell characterised by suffering discomfort and eternal anguish. It is belief to be a place of torment that burns with fire and sulphur eternally for those who reject the Lordship of Jesus and sinners who denigrate the offer of salvation

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the resurrection of the dead and eternal life in paradise for those who accept the Lordship of Jesus as well as eternal damnation for those who rejected the Lordship of Jesus

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Paradise is described as a place above the earth.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

Notes: Hell, the place of eternal damnation is described as a place beneath the earth.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The group believes that a person can only die once

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the preference of individual members and their church affiliation. The association does not play a part in this or dictate the process to be followed

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: As believers with affiliation to evangelical or protestant congregation, it is common to bury members in church or public cemetery or burial grounds

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Bible to which the group subscribes and believes makes reference to God Almighty, the maker of heaven and the earth, Jesus Christ, his son and the saviour of the world, company of angels, the twenty-four elders worshipping God every moment, the living creatures who dwell in the presence of God. It also talks about Satan or the Dragon, who was a fallen angel, demons who are his lieutenants, and antichrists through whom Satan will deceive the world in the end-time

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: Although the group does not consider the supreme high god as anthropomorphic, they still conceive of him as one who possesses human attributes.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god superintends over the whole universe. Although his abode is said to be above the earth, he is not limited to the sky as his power is felt everywhere.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: All humans are conceived of as emanations of the high god

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: The supreme high god is benevolent, gracious and full of mercy

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: He is got all the knowledge about the world. This includes even the knowledge not unknown to man

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: All things are under his control. He has both direct and indirect causal efficacy in the world

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: He is all good and favourable to his followers among the human community.

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god is a loving god. He establishes his favour with those who love him.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in divination practices

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: He speaks to the members of the group through various means. The religious specialists are only one of the several channels through which the supreme high god speaks with the members of the group.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: He speaks to the members of the group through various means. The monarch/leader of the group is only one of the several channels through which the supreme high god speaks with the members of the group.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: He also speaks through the pages of the bible/scriptures, through prayers etc

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Human spirits can be felt through diverse manifestation of such spirits

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - Notes: It is believed that they operate as territorial demons

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - No

- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Human spirits operating within a particular territory can have a per-knowledge of what is going to happen to a person and try to block it if it beneficial to the person

- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits possessed by devilish spirit or satanic spirit can through diabolical power know what will happen to a person in the future

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: This is because they operate in conjunction with devilish or demonic spirits

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– No

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: Human spirits may communicate with humans through specialists but are not restricted in communicating with humans through the specialists only.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They can work together. They can also perform some lying wonders or esoteric miracles
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Some supernatural beings, especially those loyal to Satan are domain specific.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The Bible makes reference to the fact that the eyes of the Lord run to and fro the whole earth watching over everyone and our deeds. This will form the basis of how every human will be judged at the end of the age. The Bible also relates to the Holy Spirit of God filling every believer and in-dwelling them, teaching them to do, live and act right and warning them to abstain from all sinful acts through his still small voice, prompting, dream, open vision or revelation or sometimes speaking audibly to them if it becomes absolutely necessary especially when they are encumbered and do not seem to hear him speak silently to them

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme being and his assistants do not care about food taboos but Satan and his demons sometimes spell out certain foods those who worship them must never eat or touch.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Sacred spaces are meant to be hallowed. Therefore the supreme being sometimes punishes those who behave in profane manners in sacred arena.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Sacred objects like the scriptures are meant to be hallowed. Those who subject them to profane use may be punished.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is forbidden. The ten commandments stated in the scripture is expressly against it. Murder in the New Testament of the scripture is extended to cover hatred of a brother

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: God is against a believer committing murder of anyone whether a member of the group or other religions

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: The scripture expressly state that a believer should not engage in adultery. Sex is only permitted within the limits or confines of a marriage relationship

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest is forbidden and is seriously frowned at

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

Notes: No other sexual practices contrary to the scripture is allowed

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: It is considered a sin to tell lie and is punishable by being condemned or damned

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: It is considered that it is better not to make a vow than to make one and not keep it. Generally however, taking oaths except in relation with legal practices or modern government court appearance is not allowed. The Bible teaches that our yes must be yes and our no must be no, no swearing or taking oath at all

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible preaches hardwork and condemns laziness, and that a lazy man must not eat

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible teaches that a sorcerer or a witch must not live. Sorcery is seriously condemned

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: God is against fighting in whatever form, lethal or non-lethal

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Notes: God encourages us to face challenges and problems but to not deliberately courting or rousing or raising it

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: We are admonished to care for the elderly and respect them

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: We are encouraged not to be busybodies in other people's affairs but to mind our own

business

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: We are encouraged not to engage in criminal activity of any type including property crime

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– No

Notes: There are no ritual observance whatever. The only form of ritual observance God accept is thanksgiving and praises

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: God delights in bringing into the kingdom of God those who have not known him or confess the Lordship of Jesus so that they will not perish. Knowing God through Jesus Christ opens the door to eternal salvation and blissful reign with Christ in heaven

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible makes reference to the use of just weight, fair measure, fair wages, not cheating ourselves in commercial transactions, paying labourer fair wages, not taking usury on loans, not taking people cloak for inability to pay back debts

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: God is holy and wants us to live holy. This involves being holy in the spirit: our thought, words and deeds and being holy in the way we live, where we live. Our environment must be clean because cleanliness is considered next to Godliness. There are rules for cleansing and sanctifying those who pollute themselves or are polluted by what happen to them

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: God expect us to care for others, consider them better than ourselves, give unto others and pray for other people. We must not be too encumbered with ourselves to the detriment or neglect of the good of others

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that at the end of the age, Jesus Christ is coming again to apportion rewards on the basis of the lives human beings generally and believers have lived. These rewards are blessing for those who did what is right and punishment for the wicked. Besides Satan often inflicts punishments in the form of sickness on those who not live right

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: It could be in form of affliction or oppression, sudden death or deadly diseases

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: It could be by demonic oppression

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: One can suffer for what one has done in the past. Someone for instance who committed several abortions may not have children if the womb is damaged in the process

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Human beings could repay the evil someone has done even when they did not themselves before. Government may inflict punishment in form of prison sentence for offences committed either in the past or presently

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Notes: None that I know of

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: It relates to eternal damnation; suffering in hellfire for the whole of eternity

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment that could take different forms according to the scripture generally involves discomfort

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: It is believed that humans will only live once and after death it is judgement

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: No reincarnation in any form whatsoever

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: It is not highly emphasised but it is believed that God visit punishment on believers or humans who are not living right and do not change their way

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: sometimes but not always

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: The belief among members like other Christian group who believe in the Bible in the inerrant word of God is that it is only God that brings rewards in accordance with our faith and work too.

– No

Notes: There can however be angelic visitation to bring God's blessings or inform a person about what God will do either now or in the future

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The Messiah's whereabouts are known. He is believed to be in heaven preparing a place for the saints. However, his time of return is not known as he has come to the earth once to work out the plans of salvation for the human race. He is coming back at a time not specified to take the saints home.

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Jesus Christ is coming to redeem his followers and judge the world

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: Though eschaton is a future event the group beliefs in, they do not talk about it as an event whose specific time of occurrence is known.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: They must keep evangelising so all tongues and tribes may hear the gospel. It is after they have fulfilled this that the end of this dispensation will come.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

Notes: The millennial reign that will come after Christ's second coming is the start of a new temporal cycle.

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: The saints who inherit eternity with God will no longer live under democracy, monarchy or any other form of human government. They will live under God's theocratic government.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Only those who truly live in accordance with God's will shall survive the eschaton.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Only those who truly live in accordance with God's will shall survive the eschaton.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: The group emphasises that life itself is a battle. On the premise of life being a battle in itself, they believe that courage is needed to forge ahead in life.

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
– Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes

- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: The inner beauty which stands for strength of character is preferred above physical beauty or attractiveness.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Compassion, Godliness, endurance etc

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: The practice of homosexuality and bestiality are not permitted

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Lesbianism and bestiality are not permitted

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: It is not prescribed or documented. It depends on individual decision or choice

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: But any member can chose to give sacrificially (money property, bequest) for the printing of the Bible

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at

meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Members are expected in regular weekly prayer meetings, monthly cabinet meetings (as a member of the cabinet) monthly camp (business) meetings, quarterly area leaders meeting, quarterly state and national leaders meetings, weekly bible distribution programmes, regular witnessing and occasional bible blitzes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: What is required is simple faith in the Lord Jesus.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: But sometimes individuals who could not bring themselves to agree with the basic tenets of the association or who feel affected by their activities could prove hostile or act in hostility to the group members either by denigrating members or obstructing their activities.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Zonal meetings State Conventions, National conventions and International conventions of the group are large scale rituals members are encouraged to attend

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 1000

Notes: The number of attendees depend on the nature of each program. There may be 100, 500, 5000 members in large scale rituals

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 2

Notes: This also depends on the nature of the program. Some programs are weekly, monthly,

annually etc

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: Intoxicants are highly discouraged among the members

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A community. A community in this sense is a group of people who lived together irrespective of their religious affiliation, status, ethnicity and other differences in their background. It is from this community that the association draws its membership on the basis of pre-defined criteria/requirements. It is also in the context of this community and to members of this community that the association operate or relates. In this context the Nigeria society as a whole and the seven states into which the association divides the country constitutes the community. At the level of each

states, there are now towns and villages (that constitute camps) that provides the immediate operating environment for the association.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: But it provides assistance to members in need

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The group encourages regular visit to members particularly those that are sick, bereaved, facing unpleasant situation or those not seen in any group meeting for a while. Essentially, the group encourages regular exchange of visits among members, as well as caring and support especially at the individual level and occasionally at group level

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There are officers appointed to run the office at the national level under the leadership of the national executive director and members relate with them to ensure that messages sent and funds remitted are properly documented.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They do depending on their relationship with such institutions and their bureaucracy

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: But the group requires each members to register or renew his/her membership every year with a reasonable and affordable sum of money. It is the ability to pay or renew membership dues that enables a person to retain his membership of the association.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members are required to pay taxes to the government of Nigeria as responsible citizens.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the association as Nigerian citizens interact with officers and men of the Nigeria Police Force among other armed forces.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members interact with the Nigerian Judicial system as necessary.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subject to punishment enforced by the government or any of its agencies.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: This is only applicable for capital offenses which often times are crimes against the state or crimes involving the termination of human lives. However, members of the group are known to be law abiding and responsible citizens. They are hardly, if ever, found in crimes at all talk more of crimes of this nature

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: This could occur if the said properties are established to be proceeds of crime or those obtained by false pretence

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subject to the legal code provided by the government of Nigeria and its institutions.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members are free to participate in the military provided by the government of Nigeria.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are protected by the institutionalised military provided by the government.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group uses local languages and lingua franca of territories they are found in to achieve their goals.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group uses the local languages of their localities as stipulated by the government in the conduct of their legitimate activities./communication.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: But there are specific date set apart to commemorate significant activities of the association like the National day of prayer, international day of prayer, state convention, national convention and international convention

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They use the formal calendar recognised and run by the national government of their host communities across the globe.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Some of the group members are farmers who provide for their food needs while others buy food from markets around them.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Gideons International in Ngeria, The Gideons International, ed.. The Gideons International in Nigeria, Gideon Guide Book" Policies and Procedures. Edited by The Gideons International. Lagos: The Gideons I nternational, 1995.

Reference: The Gideons International in Ngeria, The Gideons International, ed.. "The gideons magazine: the jos experience". The Gideons International in Nigeria, national Office, 2023.